

Rehabilitation of maxillary defect with Zygomatic implant supported overdenture - A case report

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ABSTRACT

AIM AND BACKGROUND:

The aim of this case report is to showcase management of a patient diagnosed with post-covid mucormycosis, and operated for the same and presented with a Brown *et al.* Class II a defect. Mucormycosis, also known as zygomycosis, is a rare but severe fungal infection caused by fungi of the *Mucorales* group, recently it emerged as a serious complication in COVID-19 patients. Early detection is critical for improving outcomes and preventing the spread of the infection. In severe cases, more extensive surgery, including removal of infected bone or eye tissue, may be required.

The use of the zygoma as an anchorage site was first explored by Branemark in 1988, using customised, increased-length conventional implants. Over the past few years, Zygomatic implants have shown to be a promising alternative in patients with atrophic maxilla, congenital/acquired maxillary defects, their ability to support full-arch prostheses in cases of severe atrophy has made them a valuable option in maxillofacial reconstructive dentistry.

CASE DESCRIPTION:

This article presents a case report of a 48-year-old male patient who presented with an operated case of post-covid mucormycosis, with a Brown *et al.* Class II a defect. This case report focuses on detailed description of prosthetic rehabilitation with zygomatic implant supported with hader bar-retained overdenture.

CONCLUSION:

Considering both the increased vertical dimension and the higher financial implications of the PFM prosthesis, it was decided that the Co-Cr bar-retained overdenture would be a more suitable and practical treatment plan. The bar-retained overdenture offered the advantage of being more lightweight, cost-effective, and better suited to the patient's anatomical needs, ensuring both functional and aesthetic benefits without compromising comfort or budget. Hence, with the patient's consent, a bar retained hollow overdenture was fabricated to further decrease the weight of the prosthesis

Key words:

zygomatic implants, overdenture, hader bar, mucormycosis

CASE REPORT

INTRODUCTION:

Mucormycosis, also known as zygomycosis, is a rare but severe fungal infection caused by fungi of the *Mucorales* group, recently it emerged as a serious complication in COVID-19 patients. The infection usually begins as a painless ulcer or swelling in the mouth, which can progress to tissue necrosis. Early detection is critical for improving outcomes and preventing the spread of the infection. In severe cases, more extensive surgery, including removal of infected bone or eye tissue, may be required. The use of the zygoma as an anchorage site was first explored by Branemark in 1988, using customised, increased-length conventional implants. Antonio D'Agostino and colleagues reported a 92.24% success rate for zygomatic implants, highlighting their reliability in clinical practice.¹ Over the past few years,

Zygomatic implants have shown to be a promising alternative in patients with atrophic maxilla, congenital/acquired maxillary defects, their ability to support full-arch prostheses in cases of severe atrophy has made them a valuable option in maxillofacial reconstructive dentistry.

Case description:

A 57-year-old male presented with the chief complaint of missing teeth and difficulty in mastication since the past 16 months. The patient had contracted COVID-19, 3 years ago, following which he was diagnosed with rhinocerebral mucormycosis within the span of a month. Due to the advanced progression of the disease, the patient had to undergo bilateral maxillary sinus debridement and a total maxillectomy. Six months post-surgery, the patient presented to the Department of Prosthodontics for rehabilitation.

On extra-oral examination, there was decreased lip fullness (Fig 1) The Brown and Shaw classification system for maxillary defects—designed for reconstructive and rehabilitative purposes—categorizes defects based on vertical and horizontal components. The vertical classification (Classes I–IV) indicates the extent of the defect in a superior-inferior direction, while the horizontal component (a–d) describes the involvement of the palate and alveolar ridge. In this case, intraoral examination revealed a Brown's Class IIa defect, characterized by complete loss of the maxilla, including the hard and soft palate as well as the alveolar ridge.² (fig 2) Considering the insufficient bone volume in the maxillary arch, a zygomatic implant-supported prosthesis was planned for the patient and he was referred to the Department of oral and maxillofacial surgery for the placement of the zygomatic implants. All aseptic precautions were taken and under local anaesthesia four implants (Nobel Zygoma, Noble BioCare, Switzerland) were placed, following the quad zygoma protocol³(fig 3) The patient was then referred back to the department of prosthodontics after 4 months of healing period. Angulations for the multi-unit abutments Nobel Zygoma, Noble BioCare, Switzerland) were checked, abutments were placed and torqued in at 20 Ncm (fig 4) Open tray impression copings were placed on the abutments (Fig.5) Open tray impression copings were then splinted with dental floss and reinforced with pattern resin.(GC Pattern Resin LS)(fig.6) A custom tray was fabricated using autopolymerising acrylic resin on which an impression of the defect was built with impression compound, a definitive impression was made using polyvinyl siloxane heavy body and light body in which the copings were picked up. (fig 7) The impression was poured with type 4 dental stone (Kalabhai Kalrock Diestone) and definitive cast was obtained. A verification jig was fabricated and checked intraorally for passivity using sheffields test followed by fabrication of record base and wax rim. (fig 8,9) Jaw relation record was made after checking for esthetics and phonetics. (fig 10,11), The facebow record was made and transferred on a semi-adjustable articulator (Hanau Wide Vue) and teeth arrangement was done. Trial of the waxed-up denture was done to check the occlusion, phonetics and esthetics. (fig 11,12) A Co-Cr bar was designed on exocad software, which was then fabricated using direct metal laser sintering (DMLS) technology. The bar was checked intraorally and radiographically for fit and passivity using the sheffield test. (fig 13) The final prosthesis was then fabricated using heat cure acrylic resin (DPI Heat Cure) (Fig 15), and the intaglio surface was trimmed to accommodate the Co-Cr hader bar with resilient attachments. The resilient clips which seated onto the hader bar were picked up with autopolymerising resin, then the denture which was relined with long term chairside soft liner. (fig 16,17). In Patients front profile the lip fullness and enhanced esthetics can be well appreciated (Fig.18)

DISCUSSION:

Unlike congenital defects, acquired maxillary defects result in sudden physiological and aesthetic changes. The extent of tissue resection significantly affects the patient's functional abilities, emotional well-being, and social interactions. A range of reconstructive and prosthetic rehabilitation options are available, each with its own advantages and limitations. Surgical reconstruction, while often pursued, is frequently accompanied by postoperative morbidity, the need for multiple revision surgeries, and unpredictable outcomes. Moreover, a removable prosthesis is typically still required to restore dentition and functional capabilities.

In this case, two viable treatment options were considered for the patient.

The first option involved a porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) splinted prosthesis along with a definitive obturator, while the second option was a Co-Cr bar-supported overdenture. Upon taking the jaw relation record, it was observed that the patient exhibited an increased vertical dimension. This finding raised concerns regarding the suitability of a splinted porcelain-fused-to-metal (PFM) prosthesis, as it would have resulted in a bulky and heavy restoration, potentially

causing discomfort and functional issues for the patient. Additionally, the cost of a PFM prosthesis would have been significantly higher.

Taking into account both the increased vertical dimension and the higher financial implications of the PFM prosthesis, it was decided that the Co-Cr Hader bar-retained overdenture would be a more suitable and practical treatment plan. Bar retained implant overdentures may exhibit high implant and prosthesis survival rates (>97%) and a limited incidence of technical complications after a mean observational period of >7 years.⁴ The bar-retained overdenture offered the advantage of being more lightweight, cost-effective, and better suited to the patient's anatomical needs, ensuring both functional and aesthetic benefits without compromising comfort or budget. Hence, with the patient's consent, a bar retained hollow overdenture was fabricated to further decrease the weight of the prosthesis.

CONCLUSION:

Globally, the incidence of mucormycosis is estimated to range from 0.005 to 1.7 cases per million population. In India, the prevalence of mucormycosis is significantly higher, estimated at approximately 140 cases per million population, 80 times higher than that observed in developed countries. Many of these cases are often diagnosed at an advanced stage, requiring extensive surgical intervention. Following surgery, patients typically undergo a long and challenging rehabilitation process, focusing not only on functional recovery but also on restoring aesthetics. In this context, the role of a prosthodontist becomes crucial. In this case, careful consideration of the patient's anatomical limitations was undertaken, leading to the design and fabrication of a fixed-removable prosthesis that ensures optimal function, form, and comfort for the patient. Prosthodontists are key in managing the rehabilitation of these patients, helping to restore lost functions and improve the appearance of affected areas, thereby significantly enhancing the patient's quality of life post-treatment. A well-crafted prosthesis also plays a vital role in boosting the patient's confidence. It helps patients regain a sense of normalcy and enhances their psychological well-being, contributing to a more positive and empowered recovery journey.

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Fig 1: Extra-oral Frontal View

Fig 2: Intra-oral occlusal view of maxillary arch showing Browns class 2a defect

Figure 1 : Intra-oral view showing zygomatic implant placement

Fig 4: Multiunit abutments torqued

fig 5: Open tray impression copings placed on multiunit abutment.

Fig 6: Impression copings splinted with floss and reinforced with pattern resin.

Fig 7: Final pick-up impression made using polyvinyl siloxane.

Fig 8 : Verification jig

Fig 9 : Fabrication of record base and wax rim

Fig 10: Jaw relation record

Fig 10: Facebow record

Fig 11: Facebow mounted on semiadjustable articulator

fig 12: Try-in of teeth arrangement

Fig.13: Designing of hader bar on exocad software

Fig. 14: Bar tried intraorally and checked for fit and passivity.

Fig 15: Final prosthesis fabricated using heat cure acrylic resin

Fig 16: Resilient clips seated onto the hader bar

fig 17: Resilient clips picked up onto the prosthesis using autopolymerizing resin and final relining of the denture using long term chairside soft liner

Fig 18: Post-op extraoral frontal view